
Performance Evaluation of Library Facilities and Information Resources: A Survey

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Abstract

The present study examines the performance evaluation of library facilities and information resources used by students of Sree Siddaganga College of Arts, Science, and Commerce, Tumakuru, Karnataka. A survey method adopted, and a total of 280 samples were collected from the students. A well-designed questionnaire was used for data collection, and the data were analysed using SPSS (27.0). The study found that most of the male (52.1%) and female (47.9%) respondents use library resources and services. This study clearly indicates that the majority of respondents are from rural areas (63%) and that 37% are in the Arts discipline. The majority (56.1%) of the respondents visit the library daily, and 45.4% of the respondents spent less than 1 hour per day. The notable findings of the study, 62.5% of the respondents, opined that the collection of books is excellent. The present study found that 44.6% of the respondents used references very frequently. The study found that 48.9% of respondents rated the referral service as excellent. This paper identifies that the library is excellent in its collection of textbooks, dictionaries, newspapers, and e-resources, as most of the respondents positively opined on the library facilities and services.

Keywords

Library Facilities, Information, Resources, Siddaganga, Textbooks.

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Introduction

Today, many scientific libraries around the world are charged with better management of resources and offering improved services to their patrons, as well as determining how to enhance the performance level of their organization (Zare Mehrjerdi, 2017). Libraries occupy a central position in the academic environment. The information age has made the time and space in which libraries stood as repositories and guardians of knowledge shift to an era in which both the production and consumption of information exceed the library's ability to contain it. The driving forces for these changes are globalisation, internationalisation, and standardisation (Eze Asogwa, 2014).

Academic libraries play a major role in providing the information resources required for teaching, learning, and research within their communities. The library resources and services need to be improved with time, to cater to the changing needs of the users and to address the changing information behaviour of the users. Accordingly, academic libraries need to regularly identify and understand user needs and develop strategies to fulfil them (Amarasekara & Marasinghe, 2020).

Review of Literature

According to Zare Mehrjerdi (2017), the study examined library performance evaluation in a dynamic environment using patron satisfaction. In almost all library models for patron satisfaction calculation, the proposed models are static and can find this value for a point in time rather than over a long period of time. In this paper, the author used an initial value for the patron's satisfaction level and, by taking all key factors into consideration, developed a system that calculates the patron's satisfaction trend over time. Illangarathne (2017) proposed a new framework for evaluating library performance, with the following major criteria: library efficiency, library core people processes, library environment, library users' satisfaction, library adaptability, and library capacity. The study found that library performance is significantly related to users' satisfaction with available services and the level of service efficiency.

Verma and Lalrokhawma (2018) defined user satisfaction as "the degree to which the library is able to meet the demands of the user". Libraries, as service-oriented organizations, mainly aim to provide

relevant information resources and services in order to meet the information needs of the users. Hence, it is important to provide relevant and reliable information resources and quality services that will satisfy the users. The studies conducted by Kumara et al. (2019) examine the use of e-sources among faculty members and students. A total of 2463 samples were selected from 11 state universities in Karnataka. The study found that most respondents preferred reading e-books/journals (57.8%), followed by newspapers/magazines (46%). The study found that almost all the respondents preferred to use e-sources for the academic work, and also a few of them were not aware of the gazetteers, bulletins, encyclopedias, and other e-sources.

Amarasekara & Marasinghe (2020) conducted a study to determine the purposes of using a library and to evaluate user satisfaction with the library facilities, library staff, library services, library resources, and the library website of the Open University of Sri Lanka. Study results indicated reading, searching library resources, using computers to access information, and borrowing and returning books as the major purposes of using the library. Rafi et al. (2022) evaluated the performance of professionals and academic libraries, rationalizing management and providing reliable services to the academic community. The performance assessment model covers the four components (management competence, professional experience, financial add/projects, and library services) in the context of the knowledge management model.

Objective of the Study

This study focuses on the following objectives.

- To know the demographic information of the respondents.
- To know the frequency of library visits and time spent using library resources by the students.
- To examine the frequency of use of information sources by the students.

Scope and Methodology

The data was collected from the Sree Siddaganga College of Arts, Science, and Commerce, Tumakuru. In the survey method used for the study, a structured questionnaire was designed to address the specific objectives of the research. Out of the 300 questionnaires distributed, a total of 280 were successfully completed and returned. The data

collected from the returned questionnaires were systematically analysed using SPSS (27.0).

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: Demographic information of the respondents

Demographic information		Frequency	Percentage
		(N=280)	
Gender	Male	146	52.1
	Female	134	47.9
Social background	Rural	177	63.2
	Urban	103	36.8
Course	Arts	98	35
	Commerce	103	36.8
	Science	79	28.2

The data presented in the table-1 shows the demographic information of the respondents. The study population consisted of a majority of the respondents are male (52.1%) and female (47.9%) respondents. The study clearly indicates that the majority of the respondents are from the rural areas (63.2%) and 36.8% of respondents are from urban areas. Further, the table also reveals that, 36.8% of the respondents are from Commerce, followed by Arts (35%) and Science.

Table 2 shows the frequency of library visits and the time spent in the use of library resources. The majority (56.1%) of the respondents visits the library daily, followed by once a week (27.1%) and once a month (2.1%); twice a week (14.6%) is the percentage of the majority of those who visit the library daily. Therefore, the notable findings of the study show that 45.4% of the respondents spent less than 1 hour per day, followed by 1-2 hours (31.8%), 2-3 hours (18.2%) and few of them spent more than 3 hours (4.6%).

Table 2: Frequency of library visits and time spent using library resources

Frequency	Frequency	Percentage	
	(N=280)		
Frequency of library visit	Daily	157	56.1
	Twice a week	41	14.6
	Once a week	76	27.1
	Once in a month	6	2.1
Time duration	<1 hours	157	56.1
	1-2 hours	41	14.6

2-3 hours	76	27.1
>3 hours	6	2.1

Table 3 shows the evaluation of information sources used by students. The table shows that the majority, 62.5% of the respondents, opined that the collection of books is excellent, followed by dictionaries (60.0%), newspapers (56.1%), E-resources (54.6%), and magazines (53.9%). The library excels in its collection of textbooks, dictionaries, newspapers, and e- resources, which are rated positively by more than half of the respondents.

The frequency of use of Information services by students is presented in Table 4. The present study found that, 44.6% of the respondents used references very frequently. The circulation service, with 42.9%

of respondents using it very frequently, is another core library function. This aligns with traditional library activities, such as borrowing and returning books for regular academic use. While still a substantial number, 33.6% of respondents very frequently use the Internet facility, which is lower than for the reference and circulation services.

Table 5 shows the rating of the library information services. The study found that 48.9% of the respondents rated the reference service as excellent, followed by circulation services (40.7%), Internet facility (36.4%), reprographic service (16.4%), and display of new arrivals (10.7%).

Table 3: Evaluation of information sources used by students (N=280)

Information sources	Excellent	Very good	Good	Average	Poor
Textbooks	175(62.5%)	59 (21.1%)	14 (5.0%)	27 (9.6%)	5 (1.8%)
Magazines	151(53.9%)	72 (25.7%)	23 (8.2 %)	25 (8.9%)	9 (3.2%)
Question bank	144(51.4%)	76 (27.1%)	25 (8.9%)	34(12.1%)	1 (.4%)
Newspapers	157(56.1%)	52 (18.6%)	20 (7.1%)	45(16.1%)	6 (2.1%)
E-resources	153(54.6%)	66 (23.6%)	29(10.4%)	37(13.2%)	3 (1.1%)
Novels	139(49.6%)	79 (28.2%)	22 (7.9%)	60(21.4%)	16 (5.7%)
Dictionaries	168(60.0%)	42(15.0%)	39(13.9%)	25 (8.9%)	6 (2.1%)
Encyclopedias	147(52.5%)	32(11.4%)	40(14.3%)	32(11.4%)	29(10.4%)
General knowledge books	71 (25.4%)	104(37.1%)	50(17.9%)	32(11.4%)	23 (8.2%)
Short stories	113(40.4%)	86 (30.7%)	23 (8.2%)	39(13.9%)	19 (6.8%)
Journals	137(48.9%)	57 (20.4%)	27 (9.6%)	36(12.9%)	23 (8.2%)

Table 4: Frequency of use of the Information services (N=280)

Information services	Very frequently	Frequently	Some time	Rarely	Never
Reference service	125 (44.6%)	96 (34.3%)	17(6.1%)	32(11%)	10(3.6%)
Circulation services	120 (42.9%)	109 (38.9%)	15(5.4%)	26(9.3%)	10(3.6%)
Display of new arrivals	91 (32.5%)	115 (41.1%)	26(9.3%)	31(11%)	16(6.1%)
Internet facility	94 (33.6%)	125 (44.6%)	14 (5%)	46(16%)	1 (.4%)
Reprographic service	92 (32.9%)	125 (44.6%)	16(5.7%)	29(10%)	18(6.4%)

Table-5: Rating of Information Services by Students (N=280)

Information services	Excellent	Very good	Good	Average	Poor
Reference service	137(48.9%)	61 (21.8%)	43(15.4%)	27 (9.6%)	12(4.3%)
Circulation services	114(40.7%)	88 (31.4%)	36(12.9%)	34(12.1%)	8 (2.9%)
Display of new arrivals	30 (10.7%)	125(44.6%)	48(17.1%)	58(20.7%)	19(6.8%)
Internet facility	102(36.4%)	53(18.9%)	58(20.7%)	53(18.9%)	14 (5%)
Reprographic service	46 (16.4%)	120(42.9%)	37(13.2%)	55(19.6%)	22(7.9%)

Discussion and Conclusion

The present study found several interesting findings regarding the use of information sources and library

services by students of Sree Siddaganga College of Arts, Science, and Commerce, Tumakuru. Firstly, the majority (52.1%) of respondents are male, followed by female respondents (47.9%). The notable findings of the study 63% majority of the students are from rural areas. It reflects the college's efforts to reach out to students from rural backgrounds, possibly through scholarships, outreach programs, and collaborations with local schools. Students from rural areas often have strong aspirations for higher education as a means of social mobility and economic advancement. This can explain their significant representation in college admissions. Urban students, on the other hand, may have more choices and access to specialized institutions within their cities.

Secondly, the study found that, among information sources, the majority of students (44.6%) reported using references very frequently. This could reflect a strong reliance on the expertise of library staff or specialized resources for in-depth research or academic projects. The circulation service, which is used very frequently, is another core function of the library. This aligns with traditional library activities, such as borrowing and returning books for regular academic use.

Finally, the library excels in its collection of textbooks, dictionaries, newspapers, and e-resources, which are rated positively by more than half of the respondents. However, the general book collection and the encyclopedia collection are areas where improvements can be made to better meet user expectations. Specifically, upgrading the general collection and addressing the inadequacies of the encyclopedias may enhance overall user satisfaction.

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